

Advanced Clearing Model in Prosumer Centric Local Flexibility Market

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Abstract—The local flexibility market models have emerged as a market-based solution to respond to the challenges that the increase in distributed energy resources caused in the power and energy systems. Using Smart Grid enabling technologies, consumers and prosumers are prepared to respond to any possible demand-side flexibility event. In this scope, this work presents an advanced bidding model for the prosumers/consumers' participation in a local flexibility market to solve existing issues in the local grid. The proposed advanced model consists of a single-sided auction-based clearing method where prosumer offers are ranked and chosen according to the price and other characteristics, such as their location and distance to the problem to be solved. The aim is to prioritize and select the offers that have a more positive impact on the situation to solve at the lowest possible cost.

Index Terms—Clearing, Demand-side flexibility, Local flexibility market, Prosumer.

I. INTRODUCTION

The European Union (EU) targets to reach a share of 50% of renewable-based energy and a cut of at least 40% of greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 [1]. To achieve this situation in the future holds an increase in renewable energies and distributed energy resources, which creates problems in supplying the right amounts of energy to community households due to the uncertainty of the energy produced in each period. Article 16 of the “Proposal for a Directive of European Parliament and of the Council on Common Rules for the Internal Market in Electricity” [1] defines the concept of Local Energy Community (LEC). It was considered a capable approach for managing the energy at the community level. LECs can better engage electricity end-users. They are citizen-led renewable energy cooperatives, housing associations, foundations, or charities, not commercial actors but produce energy meant for self-consumption [2]. Considering the LEC's characteristics, the Aggregator entity can use end-user aggregation to create demand flexibility exchanges. Hence, the concept of Local Flexible Markets (LFM) is a market-based mechanism to manage the flexibility achieved at the LEC level, which can be used for multiple purposes [3].

LFMs represent essential elements of these scenarios, allowing demand flexibility trading between community participants, energy aggregators, and distribution system operators [4]. Moreover, the significant increase in renewable energy generation, the appearance of new electrical loads, such as electric vehicles (EVs), and the guidelines to consider electricity end-users as a central entity in the power system cause changes in the power system management. With the growing volume of distributed renewable energy resources installations, the dispatch went from centralized to decentralized. Across the demand side, with the controllable assets and storage systems, it is possible to gather flexibility that needs to be managed adequately to balance the unpredictability of renewable-based generation.

The LFMs are platforms for trading flexibility inside a local community, where the energy aggregator provides a place for exchanging flexibility and sharing information. Thus, the energy aggregator acts as a community facilitator and tries to improve the local grid balance and the market exchanges. These LFMs are voluntary and allow direct transactions between community members, monetizing the flexibility sold. One of the objectives of these markets is to incentivize the consumers to become prosumers by curtailing excessive demand or installing renewable-based generation in their households for self-consumption by creating a marketplace where prosumers can make the most out of the flexibility they hold. Ultimately, this is beneficial not only for the prosumers who sell their flexibility to reduce their electricity bill but also for the consumers who can obtain energy at lower costs by participating in these markets [3].

Usually, the acquisition of flexibility on the demand side can be achieved considering market-based or control-based methods [4]. Faia et al. [5] present a market-based approach where the Distribution System Operator (DSO) buys flexibility from a small community to solve grid congestion problems. On the other hand, control-based methods are associated with demand-side management methods where an entity (DSO, Aggregator, or VPP) has control over the assets (batteries, EV, dispatchable loads) and can coordinate them to avoid the anticipated problems [6].

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This work proposes a method considering a market-based approach to buy flexibility from the demand side to solve power system management issues. The solution can solve line and transformer congestions and buses' voltage issues. The system comprises three different entities, i.e., the DSO, the Aggregator, and the end-users (consumers or prosumers). The DSO is responsible for managing the local grid, requesting flexibility from the Aggregator when needed. The Aggregator, in turn, selects the flexibility offers submitted by the end-users using a merit order method in a single-sided auction-based (asymmetric pool) market model. The novelty of the proposed method lies in the way in which the flexibility offers are ordered for selection. Instead of using only the unit price to sort the offers, it also considers the distance from the player to the location of the power grid's issue to solve and the amount of the consumption reduction.

This paper comprises five sections. After the introductory section, the methodology is explained, presenting some implementation details. Section III presents the case study with the electrical network description, and section **Error! Reference source not found.** details the analyses and discussion of the results. Finally, section V concludes with this work's findings and perspectives for future work.

II. METHODOLOGY

The proposed methodology considers a market-based approach to solve grid management issues by purchasing demand-side flexibility to local consumers or prosumers. The problems addressed by this work's solution include line and transformer congestions, and voltage issues in buses. Figure 1 presents the conceptual workflow of the suggested resolution.

Figure 1. Proposed methodology flowchart

As Figure 1 demonstrates, this work's methodology includes the DSO, an energy Aggregator from a local grid, and respective players (i.e., consumers and prosumers). The DSO is responsible for managing the local grid. To this end, he starts by running the power flow analysis for a given distribution network for the 24-hourly periods of the next day, considering forecasted demand and generation. If the DSO detects any

issue, he requests demand flexibility from the Aggregator responsible for the respective area for the periods where the problems occur.

After receiving the DSO's request, the Aggregator requests demand flexibility from his aggregated players, who send their offers considering the hourly period, the available demand flexibility, and unit price. For each period, the Aggregator ranks the offers according to the proposed unit price, amount of available demand flexibility, and distance from the player to the location of the grid's problem to solve, determining the offers' order of acceptance. Next, the Aggregator selects the first of the previously sorted offers and runs a power flow analysis to confirm if the issue(s) identified are solved for the respective period. It is an iterative process until the power flow analysis returns no problems or there are no more offers available for that hour. If all issues are solved, the Aggregator communicates the LFM's results to the DSO and his players. On the following day, if the demand flexibility is enough to avoid the foreseen problems, the DSO remunerates the Aggregator, who, in turn, pays the players that provided their demand flexibility. The offer with the maximum unit price among the selected ones determines the clearing price paid to these players per power unit.

However, if, in any period, it is not possible to solve the grid problems identified, the Aggregator informs the DSO so that he tries to buy the necessary demand from a neighbor grid or the wholesale market. The following subsections present the power flow analysis performed by the DSO and Aggregator and the clearing model conducted by the Aggregator to order and select the players' demand flexibility offers, respectively.

A. Power Flow Analysis

The power flow analysis performed by the DSO and the Aggregator considers different metrics, namely the buses' voltage limits and angle deviations, the lines' congestions, and the transformers' congestions. For the verification and validation of these metrics, the following equations apply.

Equation (1) represents the rule to verify if the voltage of a given bus is within the minimum and maximum allowed limits.

$$V_{min} \leq V_{b,t} \leq V_{max}, \forall b \in \Omega_b, \forall t \in T \quad (1)$$

where, $V_{b,t}$ is the voltage of bus b in period t , V_{max} is the maximum allowed voltage value and V_{min} is the minimum, usually $1.05 pu$ and $.95 pu$, respectively.

Equation (2) represents the constraint to validate if the angle deviation of a given bus is within the maximum and minimum limits.

$$\theta_{min} \leq \theta_{b,t} \leq \theta_{max}, \forall b \in \Omega_b, \forall t \in T \quad (2)$$

where, $\theta_{b,t}$ is the angle deviation of bus b in period t , and θ_{max} and θ_{min} are the respective maximum and minimum allowed values.

Equation (3) represents the condition that confirms if the power flow is below or equal to the maximum permitted by a given line or transformer.

$$0 \leq FlowS_{l,t} \leq FlowS_l^{max}, \forall l \in \Omega_l, \forall t \in T \quad (3)$$

where, $FlowS_{l,t}$ is the power flow of line (or transformer) l in period t , and $FlowS_l^{max}$ is the respective maximum accepted power flow for line (or transformer) l .

Equation (4) allows to calculate the apparent power flow in each line or transformer.

$$FlowS_{l,t} = \sqrt{P_{l,t}^2 + Q_{l,t}^2}, \forall l \in \Omega_l, \forall t \in T \quad (4)$$

where, $P_{l,t}$ and $Q_{l,t}$ represent the active and reactive power flow of line (or transformer) l in period t .

Equations (5) and (6) represent the restrictions to guarantee that a given supplier's active and reactive powers are within authorized limits.

$$0 \leq P_{supplier,t} \leq P_{supplier}^{max}, \forall t \in T \quad (5)$$

$$0 \leq Q_{supplier,t} \leq Q_{supplier}^{max}, \forall t \in T \quad (6)$$

where, $P_{supplier,t}$ and $Q_{supplier,t}$ are the active and reactive power of *supplier* in period t , and $P_{supplier}^{max}$ and $Q_{supplier}^{max}$ are the maximum allowed values for the active and reactive power of *supplier*, respectively. As is typical in distribution networks considering only households, the transformer ensures the reactive power, covering the lines' reactive losses since the consumer loads are purely resistive.

B. Advanced Clearing Model

The advanced clearing model proposed in this work is inspired in the single-sided auction market mechanism (i.e., asymmetrical pool). In the asymmetrical pool, supply offers are ordered from the lowest to the highest unit price. After, if the demand is lower than the total supply, supply offers are accepted until all the demand is satisfied. Otherwise, all supply offers are purchased. The clearing (market) price is determined by the last supply offer accepted. Figure 2 illustrates the asymmetrical pool mechanism.

Figure 2. Asymmetrical pool mechanism [7]

The main difference between the proposed advanced clearing model and the asymmetrical pool model is the ordering of the offers. The accepted demand flexibility offer with the highest unit price sets the LFM clearing price, similar to the asymmetrical pool.

To order the demand flexibility offers, the proposed solution considers three components, namely the offer's unit price (EUR/kWh), the amount of demand flexibility (kWh) available for reduction, and the distance (m) from the player presenting the offer to the location of the grid's issue to be solved. Using these three elements, the Aggregator calculates a weighted cost to sort the received demand flexibility offers from the lowest to the most expensive and clears the LFM.

Equation (7) represents a demand flexibility offer submitted by a player for a specific hourly period.

$$offer_{p,t} = \{price_{p,t}; reduction_{p,t}\}, \forall p \in P, \forall t \in T \quad (7)$$

where, $offer_{p,t}$ is demand flexibility offer of player p in period t , $price_{p,t}$ is the offer's unit price in EUR/kWh and $reduction_{p,t}$ is the offer's amount of demand reduction in kWh.

Equations (8) to (10), in turn, are used by the Aggregator to calculate the weighted cost of each demand flexibility offer received per period. These equations consider the grid's operational costs to calculate the weighted cost for each demand flexibility offer, aiming to minimize the final total operating cost to solve the problem(s) in hands.

Equation (8) determines the operational cost of a given player's power transaction in the grid.

$$CT_p = CT * \frac{P_p * X_p}{\sum_{p=1}^{Np} P_p * X_p} \quad (8)$$

where, CT_p is the total cost of the power transaction of player p , CT is the total cost of all transactions for the DSO, P_p is the consumption of player p , X_p is the distance (measured by the sum of the lines' length) from player p to the grid's issue location, and Np is the total number of players.

Equation (9) calculates the operational cost of a given player's power transaction in the grid after reduction.

$$CT_p^{red} = CT * \frac{(P_p - P_p^{red}) * X_p}{(\sum_{p=1}^{Np} P_p * X_p) - P_p^{red} * X_p} \quad (9)$$

where, CT_p^{red} , is the total cost of the power transaction of player p considering the offered reduction was accepted, and P_p^{red} is the amount of demand flexibility offered.

Equation (10) determines the weighted cost to be assigned to each demand flexibility offer.

$$w_p^{red} = \frac{CT_p - CT_p^{red}}{CT_p} \quad (10)$$

where, w_p^{red} is the weight to assign to a period's offer submitted by player p .

Equation (11) represents a demand flexibility offer submitted by a player for a specific hourly period after setting the respective weighted cost.

$$new\ offer_{p,t} = \{price_{p,t};\ reduction_{p,t};\ w_{p,t}^{red}\} \quad (11)$$

Using the weighted demand flexibility offers, the Aggregator ranks and orders the received reduction proposals from the lowest cost to the highest. After, the Aggregator clears the LFM by selecting the necessary offers until, ideally, all grid constraints are respected. If, for a given period, all grid issues are solved, the period's demand flexibility offer with the highest unit price sets the clearing price. Otherwise, he must inform the DSO what problems weren't possible to solve and in which periods.

The model proposed in this work includes spatial details (i.e., distance) aiming to solve the local grid issues at the lowest cost possible and with the closest possible player(s). Additionally, depending on the type(s) of issue(s) to solve, the Aggregator decides to which players send the requests for demand flexibility. E.g., in the case of congestion in a line or transformer, the Aggregator only requests demand flexibility from downstream players regarding the congested element since the consumption reduction from upstream players will not influence the congestion. On the other hand, if there's a problem with the voltage magnitude, all players are invited to participate.

The following section presents a case study scenario to demonstrate the use of the proposed methodology.

III. CASE STUDY

The present case study aims to demonstrate the applicability of the proposed LFM clearing model. To this end, the IEEE European Low Voltage (LV) test feeder [8] is considered for this case study's scenario. Figure 3 illustrates a reduced electrically equivalent model of the IEEE European LV test feeder.

Figure 3. Reduced electrically equivalent IEEE European LV test feeder [9]

The IEEE European LV test feeder comprises 55 loads, 906 buses, and 904 lines in a radial structure connected to a medium-voltage (MV) transformer (800 kVA), stepping the voltage from 11kV to 416 kV. Thus, this distribution grid connects to a MV network. The present scenario considers 13 consumers, and the remaining 42 loads are prosumers with photovoltaic panels (PV) installed. The PV generation is only for self-consumption, not fully covering the demand needs of each prosumer.

Figure 4 presents the average demand and generation profiles of the consumers and prosumers considered for the case study's scenario.

Figure 4. Player's average demand and generation profiles

The average demand among all the periods is 85.86 kWh, and its peak is in period 12 at 140 kWh. The daily consumption is 2060.65 kWh. Regarding PV generation, the average generation throughout the day is 17.84 kWh, and its peak is in period 15 at 73.99 kWh. The total PV generation for the 24-hour periods is 428.31 kWh.

Figure 5 presents the electricity and feed-in tariffs for the consumers and prosumers.

Figure 5. Electricity (Buy price) and feed-in (Sell price) tariffs

As shown in Figure 5, the electricity tariff (Buy price) is a tri-hourly tariff at 0.102 EUR/kWh in off-peak periods, 0.169 EUR/kWh in medium peak periods, and 0.235 EUR/kWh in high peak periods. On the other hand, the nationally regulated feed-in (Sell price) tariff is flat at 0.045 EUR/kWh.

Finally, to run the power flow analysis performed by the DSO and the Aggregator is used the previously developed Power Flow Service (PFS) [10]. PFS is a publicly available web service allowing the definition and evaluation of electrical grids through their power flow analysis. The DSO and the Aggregator run PFS for each simulation period, receiving as a response not only the power flow calculation but also the issues that may occur.

IV. RESULTS

This section focuses on evaluating and comparing the results of the proposed LFM model with the well-known asymmetrical pool model. Table I presents an overview of the daily results for the day-head evaluation of the power flow analysis: without LFM (No-LFM); after the LFM considering the base asymmetrical pool model (LFM-Asy); and, in turn, using the LFM advanced clearing model (LFM-ACM) proposed by this work.

TABLE I. DAY-AHEAD RESULTS OVERVIEW

	No-LFM	LFM-Asy	LFM-ACM
Total Consumption (kWh)	2310.80	2287.56	2289.26
Total Generation (kWh)	428.32	428.35	428.31
Total Losses (kVAh)	29.36	25.21	25.35
External Supply (kVAh)	1911.84	1884.42	1886.30
No. Periods w/ Violations	1	0	0
No. Buses' Violations	208	0	0
No. Lines' Violations	0	0	0

From the results presented in Table 1 it is possible to observe a decrease in the total losses from the No-LFM case to the LFM-Asy and LFM-ACM cases. The external supply also decreases from the No-LFM to the other two cases. The initial power flow analysis (No-LFM) identifies 208 buses with voltage above the maximum allowed limit. In turn, both LFM-Asy and LFM-ACM cases eliminate all violations.

Table II presents the results of both LFM's clearing models in period with the most consumption, i.e., period 12. Period 12 is, in fact, the period where the issues occur according to the power flow day-ahead analysis. As it is possible to observe in Figure 4, besides being the period with most demand, the PV generation also drops from periods 11 to 13, which might reflect a cloudy weather forecast in those periods. Since the problem identified is related to voltage control, the Aggregator requests flexibility to all his players.

TABLE II. MODELS COMPARISON FOR THE PEAK-CONSUMPTION PERIOD

	LFM-Asy	LFM-ACM
Period	12	12
No. Offers	55	55
No. Accepted Offers	24	35
Clearing Price (EUR/kWh)	0.047	0.030
Purchased Flexibility (kWh)	23.236	21.536
Paid value (€)	1.099	0.646
Reduction	23.236	21.536

From the analysis of the results, the proposed method (LFM-ACM) selects the demand flexibility offers that cause the most impact on the grid's issue at the lowest possible cost as it accepts a higher number of offers at a lower price.

Figure 6 and Figure 7 show the period's 12 clearing methods with the offers accepted and respective clearing prices.

Figure 6. LFM-Asy clearing for period 12

In the LFM-Asy, the purchased flexibility was 23.236 kWh, and the clearing price was 0.047 EUR/kWh. Offers above this value are not considered.

Figure 7. LFM-ACM clearing for period 12

In the LFM-ACM, the bought flexibility was 21.536 kWh, and the clearing price was 0.030 €/kWh. This price is the highest offer within the accepted offer area.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work proposes an advanced clearing model for LFM participation to solve possible grid issues, considering the offers with the most impact at the lowest cost. The results show the advantage of the presented model compared to the asymmetrical pool model. Future work includes testing scenarios with multiple simultaneous issues, and research about player's strategic bidding. Future work includes testing scenarios with multiple simultaneous issues and research on the players' strategic bidding. The evolution of the proposed methodology to include connections to MV and HV grids is also in mind.

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